

Strategic Teacher Workforce Management: Key to Sustainable Organisational Performance in Ekiti State Secondary Education

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Abstract:

This study investigated strategic teacher workforce management focusing on staff development programmes, regular promotion, and staff welfare and its relationship with organizational performance in Ekiti State public secondary schools. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, targeting a population of 204 principals and 7,538 teachers. Using a multistage sampling technique, 300 teachers were selected from 30 schools across five local government areas in each of the three senatorial districts. The first stage involved selecting local government areas, followed by schools, and finally teachers from each school using simple random sampling. Data were collected through two instruments: the Strategic Teacher Workforce Management Questionnaire (STWMQ) and the Organizational Performance Questionnaire (OPQ), both validated for face and content reliability, with test-retest reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.79, respectively. Data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed significant positive relationships between staff development, regular promotion, and staff welfare with organizational performance. Based on these results, the study recommended periodic professional development programmes to enhance pedagogical skills, timely promotion to motivate teachers and strengthen commitment, and the provision of adequate welfare packages to support effective teaching and learning. Overall, the study emphasizes that strategic workforce management practices are essential for enhancing teacher effectiveness and promoting higher organizational performance in secondary education.

Key words: Strategic, teacher, workforce, management, organisational performance,

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Introduction

The Secondary education occupies a strategic position because it is the connecting rod between the primary and the tertiary institution. Secondary education is saddled with the responsibilities of producing low level manpower as well as preparing students for higher institution of learning. The education at secondary school level provides the general training necessary for individuals for acquired skills necessary to program themselves for future career challenges. This is why Ahmad, Nasreen, Anusuyah, Shereen, Tin, and Mahfuzur (2025) opined that the need to bridge educational gaps arising from primary education and preparing students for specialization in different fields of endeavour, place fresh demands on the managers of the secondary school level of education. The management of teaching personnel in secondary schools has remained a great concern majorly to parents, managers of education, students and consumers of the products of education, because of the quality of administration, organization and achievement of set goals within the organization that is, declining in education and obviously its attendant effect on organizational performance and effectiveness. An x-ray before the civil war shows that the management of schools in Nigeria was in control of the missions and privatize individuals or organization.

History recorded that personnel management practices in educational institutions in Nigeria before and after the war according to Aja-Okorie and Chukwuemeka (2023) were branded by general poor conditions of service for teachers in the then mission and private owned primary and secondary schools. The mismanagement of schools and very poor conditions of service of the teaching personnels by the mission led the government to take over all schools. In view of this, the management of teaching personnel in secondary schools; deserve adequate attention from the stakeholders. Management of teaching workforce involves adopting strategies that will gear toward the achievement of personal (teachers) and organizational (school) goal. In the submission of Edo, and Johnson, (2024), a well managed teachers will always look for better ways to do their teaching job in order to enhanced good organizational performance in the schools. Management of teaching personnels (teacher workforce) can be through the adoption of, and or combination of these strategies, supervision, in-service training and compensation among others. Hence, any teacher that enjoys the influence of the above named strategies is likely to give all his best in discharging his or her duties such that the organization effectiveness will not be eroded. Personnel management is a set of functions and activities carried out in an organization such as the school, in a fair, affirmative and efficient manner for the benefit of the organization, individual and society. Personnel functions include, among others, recruitment, training and development, discipline, promotion, welfare, integration and effective coordination of staff with the aim of stimulating them to contribute in achieving the organizational performance. Salasiah and Ahmad (2023)

and Ahammad (2025) identified certain essential ingredients of the concept of personnel management such as motivational factor, strategic use of resources, behavioural factors, and coordination of human and organization needs.

Similarly, managing personnel is the art and process of acquiring the best manpower and effectively utilizing them through development of mobilization for the achievement of organizational effectiveness. Obviously it must be noted that no organization such as school can function effectively without professional way of managing the teaching personnels. Laiu and Voicu (2021) added that personnel management is that specialized activity of the

organization, which caters for the employment, development and utilization of the organization, human resources. Managing personnel is the art of harnessing all the human resources in an organization in order to get something done at a minimum cost and with utmost beneficial results as planned and anticipated without exploitation of the personnel.

Basically, personnel management is concerned with the recruitment, training, development, effective mobilization and utilization of organization human resources to achieve employees' goals and organizational effective. Also, every educational system at every level depends heavily on the teaching personnel especially in schools for the execution of its program. No wonder Nwaka and Ofojebe (2010) stated that teachers are the most critical resources for effective implementation and realization of the educational policies and objectives at the practical level of classroom. The maintenance and improvement of educational standards is only possible through teachers. Teachers therefore, are the most indispensable entity in the school system. In addition, they (teachers) are the greatest aid to learning. The shortage or poor management of teachers as personnel reduces the extent to which the curriculum can be delivered accurately and make the organization (school) effective. It should be sounded that the major premises of teaching personnel management in education is that the results of the educative process will be determined by the teachers who facilitate learning for self actualization and organization effectiveness.

In view of the important role of teacher workforce in organizational success (effectiveness), Lolo (2025) reported that personnel management is the key, strategic challenge for all industries including education. Rudy (2024) saw personnel management in education as the activities involving getting the teaching and non-teaching staff to work toward attainment of educational goals. The author added that the management of personnel in education is a complex process because the proper management of both staff and students will help in order to achieve the end objectives of education. The focus on personnel management in an organization like school according to Lolo (2025) are to develop the kinds of teaching personnel that would effectively perform the various tasks, provide effective leadership, create a climate conducive to maximise productivity, influence members of staff in performing effectively and assess what constitute the needs of the organization. Organizational effectiveness refers to the ability of manager of organization to harness organizational resources to achieve the set organizational goals in accordance with acceptable best practices in the world. The effectiveness of organization could be assessed based on how the institutions are performing in relation to its set goals within the confines of the national policies on education and global best practice. Some of the symptoms of organizational ineffectiveness as observed are poor supervision of teaching, learning process, lack of discipline among the staff and students, poor leadership role, ineffective communication, poor decision making, poor performance appraisal and poor resources management among others.

Consequent upon the observed deterioration in organizational performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, one wonders if organizational ineffectiveness is not a reflection of mismanagement of teacher workforce in the areas of staff development, staff promotion and staff welfare. Considering the importance of managing teaching personnel and its useful effect on organizational performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, personnel development has been observed to be the hall mark of goal achievement in

organizations (including education system) world over. The current trend in the education system also calls for teaching personnel development otherwise known as staff development. Staff development for teachers is a key mechanism for improving classroom instruction, student achievement and school effectiveness (Olaifa, Usman, Olaifa, Onikoyi & Adesina, 2025). Although, high quality staff development programmes appears to be germane to the attainment of educational goals, but there remains a shortage of such programmes in secondary schools in Ekiti State. It was observed that the majority of the teaching personnel rarely attend in-service training while those that strive to acquire additional qualifications did so at personal cost, perhaps with a view to secure another job. The inability of the government and other educational stakeholders to organize in-servicing training for teachers appears to have negatively affected instructional delivery in the classroom with its attendant effect on organizational effectiveness. However, a particular target for criticism is the prevalence of what is called single-shot, meaning one day workshops that often make teacher professional development intellectually superficial, disconnected from deep issues of curriculum and learning, fragmented and non-cumulative' due to non-coherence of infrastructure for staff development. That is why Faiqa (2024) submitted that staff training programmes for teachers are important aspects of education process that deals with the art of acquiring skills in the teaching profession. To substantiate the link between staff development and organizational performance, Kirungi, and Byaruganga, (2024) suggested staff training as a very important tool for improving the skills and performance of employees in an organization. Also as pointed out by Sacote-Labadan, and Tantiado, (2025) effective professional training produces changes in teacher's instructional practices which can be linked to improvement in school effectiveness. Previous studies have shown that successful staff development practices can impact on teachers job performance in and out of the classroom (Bibi Akbar & Borich, 2012; Uzochukwu & Ogbuabor, 2024). Olaifa, Usman, Olaif, Onikoyi and Adesina (2025) found that teachers whose in-service training was focused on the curriculum can teach well when what has been learnt was applied in the classroom. This implies schools as formal organization are usually good and effective when teachers (personnel) participated in training that focused on the curriculum. In the studies of Samundeeswari, Angayarkanni, Gopala and Sharma, (2024) on principals provision for professional growth and teachers job effectiveness, a total of 400 teachers were selected samples and analysis of the study found that making provision for the professional growth of teachers often led to greater effectiveness and consequently high organizational effectiveness.

Promotion remained a prominent facet of teaching personnel management. Promotion is the elevation of an employee for a job of higher significance and higher compensation Nyaga and Omuya (2024). The movement of an employee upward in the hierarchy of the organization leads to enhancement of responsibility and rank and improved compensation packages. Promotion motivates teachers when it is granted certain appropriate interval in the teaching service, as none would be happy when they are static in a system. It is disheartening to observe that teachers have promotion delayed in Ekiti State secondary schools in the last couple of years. Even in cases where promotion is done, the financial benefits attached to such promotions were denied the staff. When teachers are not fully promoted as and when due, they are likely to be dissatisfied with their job and this could eventually influence the process of instructional delivery which in turn may affect school or organizational success. Ekundayo and Familoni (2022) throw light on this subject that when teachers are promoted, their morale is boosted and they are motivated to put in their best for educational instructions and their contributions toward organisation objectives and goals is high.

Many researchers give their opinions that job satisfaction is strongly connected with promotion opportunities and there is a direct and positive association between promotional opportunities and job satisfaction (Nyaga & Omuya 2024; Odediji, Bamikole, Afolabi & Ekundayo, 2023). The reliance of the positive correlation before promotion and job satisfaction is on perceived justice by workers. This is because a significant fact of career of employees is promotion that enhances an employee's work experiences (Choi et al 2017). Omodo, Nsereko and Eton (2025) supported that better promotion and opportunity for further training is special intergradient needed for high organizational job performance. Reporting from a study carried out in the public secondary schools focusing on factors influencing teachers' job performance in the rural Obigala Village in Nigeria, Emenike (2011) affirmed that teachers who obtained regular promotions were motivated to increase their levels of work performance than those who were static on their grade cadre.

Similarly, focusing on a survey of motivational factors on the performance of students in internal examinations in Bureti constituency in Kericho country, Langat (2013) concluded that failure to promote teachers encourages apathy in taking up assigned responsibilities among them in most learning institutions thereby eroding high organizational effectiveness. Additionally, in school system, teachers who are regularly promoted tend to put in their best to see that their organization is effectively enhanced. In agreement with this, the finding of Noram and Zaizura (2013) in a research work shows that promotion opportunities are also an important aspect of a worker's career and life. It has a significant impact on other job characteristics such as responsibilities, loyalty and commitment. Globally speaking, an educational system can use promotion as a reward for highly productive staff with a view to making them more productive. Fakunle and Omodan (2017) concurred that there is significant relationship between promotion and job performance of academic staff. Also, Vasillios (2010) investigated the impact of promotion and promotion expectations on job performance and found that those who are promoted are more productive than those who are not and who experience delay in promotion while in spite of the other submissions, the findings of Muhammad, Rizwan and Yasin (2012) found out that promotion has less influence and is partially significant to the job performance which is a reflection of job satisfaction. Teachers are respected for their uphill-struggle and exceptional inputs, and honours are accorded to strengthen and encourage such deeds in the nearest future. The possibility of an improved organisational performance can be augmented by

taking instance to distinguish a job well done. The morale of a teacher can be enhanced and their skills sustained with the help of both affirmative as well as constructive criticism (Odediji, Bamikole Afolabi & Ekundayo, 2023). In addition, the authors submitted that promotion system places value on a fundamental phase of the organisation especially when managing teaching personnel. Teacher who is reassigned or promoted to a tenured position will be subjected to the applicable tenure renewal policy (Ekundayo & Familoni, 2022). The authors established that when teachers are promoted, their morale is heightened and they are enthused to put in their premium for the educational institutions. However, it appears there is habitually delayed in the implementation of teachers' promotion and fringe benefits that is proportionate with their positions which could affect their job productivity thereby erode the quality of organisational performance. Staff welfare is a potent tool in the management of teacher workforce in secondary school which could affect staff performance in organizations including the school system. The indicators of teaching personnel welfare include: basic salary wages, wealthy schemes, pension schemes, transport allowances, overtime allowances and incentivizes and fringe benefits Owabie, Amadi, and Ukoha (2024). Observation shows that teachers welfare seem not to be priority of the government in the state rather pay a lip says. It is commonly observed occurrence for teachers to be owed salaries in arrears. Leave bonuses remains unpaid while other benefits are unspoken of. This seems to have led to the inability of teachers to meet their basic physiological needs such as feeding, shelter among others, with this situation, one would imagine what becomes of teachers commitment and performance vis – a – vis organizational performance. Good welfare scheme may help minimize absenteeism and retain teachers in the teaching services and could contribute to good quality public education. Welfare gives and makes employees and the environment think constructively and help in improving the relationship between the workers and management (Kolawole, 2024). This may minimize strike and absenteeism hence promoting efficiency and effectiveness in the organization. In a study based on employee productivity and organizational performance, Bruce (2024) submitted that when workers have performed their duties accordingly, they will be more committed to give their best and add values to the organisation in future engagements. Ekundayo and Familoni (2022) agreed that organisational performance is directly linked to quantity and quality of the teacher's welfare packages which improve performance and need to motivate teacher using job incentives like wage increment, housing allowances or staff housing scheme, transportation allowances.

Welfare services have played vital roles in many organizations in determining effectiveness and efficiency. When working condition is conducive to the needs of workers, high employee productivity would be expected. Ikenyiri and Ihua – Maduenyi (2011) investigated teachers' assessment of needs effectiveness in Omoku-River State, Nigeria. They found out that enhancement of rent allowance (housing) was a strong predictor of teacher effectiveness which directly influence higher school or organizational success. In the work of Li, Kanchanapoom, Deeprasert, Duan, and Qi, (2025) who investigated teacher motivation and incentives in Nigeria and found out that various state governments have instituted a policy of granting a revolving loan for teachers in order to assist them build their own houses. The study further discovered that majority of the teachers thereby having a negative influence on their job performance. Where the job level or job performance of teachers is low as a result of mismanagement of teaching personnel, higher organizational effectiveness or performance cannot be guaranteed. Bola and Ojibara (2011) conducted a study on "assessment of stakeholders perceptions on the provision and management of academic and welfare services in Nigerian colleges of Education: The study purposefully find out the types of welfare and academic services provided and how these services were effectively managed to have impact on teachers behaviour so as to bring about effectiveness in the organization.

Therefore, this study examined staff development programmes (SDP), prompt staff promotion (PSP) and robust staff welfare packages (SWP) as ways of managing teacher workforce for improved organizational performance.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to pilot the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between staff development programmes and organizational performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State.
2. There is no significant relationship between staff promotion and organizational performance,
3. There is no significant relationship between staff welfare packages and organizational performance.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for this study consisted of all 204 principals and 7,538 teachers in public secondary schools in Ekiti State while the sample consisted of 300 teachers selected using multistage sampling procedure. The respondents were drawn from 30 public secondary schools within the state. First stage involved selection of 5 local government areas from each of the three senatorial districts using simple random sampling technique while in the second stage; two schools were selected from each of the local government areas using sample random sampling technique. In the third stage, 10 teachers were selected from each school using simple random sampling technique.

Two instruments were used to collect data for the study. The first one is tagged "Strategic Teacher workforce Management Questionnaire (STWMQ), the second is organizational performance Questionnaire (OPQ). Face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts and test – retest method of reliability was adopted with reliability coefficient of 0.81 and 0.79 for both instruments. The data collected were analysed using Pearson product moment correlation. The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between staff development programmes and organizational performance.

Table 1: Staff development programme and organizational performance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>No. of Schools</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>ρ</i>
Development Programme		11.23	2.78		
Organizational Performance	30	31.21	1.60	0.625*	0.000

* $\rho < 0.05$

The completed r – value (0.625) is significant at the 0.05 level of significance, as shown in Table 1. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This means that in Ekiti State, there is a considerable risk between staff Development programmes and organizational performance. It therefore established that regular staff development programmes will encourage the teachers to do their job effectively and promote better organizational success.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relation between regular promotion and organisational performance

Table 2: Regular promotion and organizational performance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>No. of Schools</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>ρ</i>
Regular Promotion		11.63	2.37		
Organizational Performance	30	31.21	1.60	0.441*	0.015

* $\rho < 0.05$

The estimated r-value (0.441) is significant at the 0.05 level of significance as indicated in table 2. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected. This implies that there is a strong relationship between regular promotion and organisational performance to Ekiti State. The result indicated that regular staff promotion as and when due will boost the morale of the teacher and as well sustain higher productivity in teaching and greatly enhance organisational performance.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between staff welfare and organisational performance.

Table 3: Staff welfare and organizational performance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>No. of Schools</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>ρ</i>
Staff welfare		14.23	2.60		
Organizational performance	30	31.21	1.60	0.584*	0.000

* $\rho < 0.05$

Table 3: revealed r-value (0.584) is significant at the 0.05 level of significance as shown in table 3. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Thus, there is positive relationship between staff welfare and organisational performance. This implies a robust staff welfare package will motivate the teacher to put in their best and be more committed to productive teaching.

Discussion

It was deduced from the findings that there was positive relationship between staff development and organisational performance. This implies that if staff development receives adequate attention from the government and school administrators, teacher productivity in teaching and other non-teaching activities will be improved upon and this will eventually impacts organisational performance. This result could be attributed to teachers' attendance of development programmes such as seminars, workshop, Conferences coupled with the personal pursuit of additional higher degree. The result agrees with the findings of Nur, Nuron, Suhaily, and Nur, (2022) which suggested that the intensive reform approach in professional development has more positive impact on organisational performance. Earlier, Olaifa, Usman, Olaifa, Onikoyi and Adesina (2025) had submitted that teachers whose in-service training focused on the curriculum can teach well when what has been learnt was applied in the classroom. Also, in consonant with the findings, of Samundeeswari, Angayarkanni, Gopala and Sharma, (2024) affirmed that making provision for the growth of teachers often led to greater effectiveness and consequently higher organisational performance. This implies that school as formal organisation are usually good and effective when teachers (personnel) participated in professional development programmes that focused on a well-structured curriculum. Similarly, Bibi, Akbar and Borich (2012), Uzochukwu and Ogbuabor, (2024) reported a positive relationship between professional development and organisational performance.

The findings also showed significant relationship between staff promotion and organisational performance. This implies that is staff are promoted as and when due, they will be motivated to perform their duties effectively, which will in turn impact positively on organisational success. This is in line with the findings of Langat (2013) who reported that the failure to promote teacher encourages apathy in taking up assigned responsibilities among them in most learning institutions which eventually leads to poor job performance and ultimately poor organisational performance. Fakunle and Omodan (2017) supported that if organisations want to accelerate performance or employees in the organisation, fair promotional opportunities should be given to employees. When promotion is given to workers an and when due, it tends to maximize staff job performance and necessitate the fact that the career need is given promptly and invariably motivate workers maximally for enhanced organisational performance.

Muhammad, Rizwan and Yasin (2012), Vasilios (2010) as well as Noraani and Zaizura (2013) agreed that the impact of promotion and promotion expectations on job satisfaction. The result showed that workers who are expecting promotion tend to be productive than those who are not and who experience delay in promotion. In addition Ekundayo and Familoni (2022) throw weight in support of these findings that when teachers are promoted, their morale is boosted and they are motivated to put in their best for educational instructions and contribute to organisation objectives and goals.

The findings from table 3 showed that there is a significant relationship between staff welfare and organisational performance. This implies that if teachers welfare packages is adequately catered for, their performance will be improve with it attendant positive effects on organisational performance. This agrees with the findings of Bola Ojibara (2011) who supported that adequate provision of welfare and academic facilities and their management were assumed by the stakeholders as he factors militating against survival of the

organisation. Ekundayo and Familoni (2022) agreed that organisational effectiveness is directly linked to quantity and quality of the teacher's welfare packages which improve performance and need to motivate teacher using job incentives like wage increment, housing allowances or staff housing scheme, transportation allowances. Also, Ojeleye (2017) revealed in support of the findings that prompt payment of workers salary as integral part of welfare packages serves as motivator to worker productivity for better organisational performance. He added that prompt payment of salary and working conditions translate into quality of instruction importantly on the effectiveness of school personnel policies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that staff development programmes, staff promotion and staff welfare packages were important components that influenced organisational performance or success for sustainable secondary schools education in Ekiti State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Periodic professional development programmes should be organised for teaching personnel on pedagogies of teaching with a view to help them improve on their performance for better organisational effectiveness.
2. Effort should be made to promote teacher workforce as and when due as this will go a long way in motivating them to be more committed to their job for enhanced organisational performance.
3. Serious attention should be paid to provision of welfare packages for the teacher workforce for effective teaching and learning activities so as to guarantee organisational success.

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